

A Computation on Any 3-Coloring Graph is a P-problem

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It is one of the open problems, whether or not the algorithm for a 3-coloring graph is in polynomial time¹⁻³. In general, the coloring problem for a graph and an integer k is to determine whether its chromatic number is at most or not; the k -colorability problem is to verify whether vertices of a given graph can be properly colored with at most k colors^{3,4}. However, the positive answer by using set theory scares us⁵. Based on the computer logic, we build up a model of chromatic space to study on graph coloring issues⁶⁻⁸. We demonstrate that 3-coloring is a P-problem by analyzing the codes in inheriting primitive operations. We cut off the edge recursion in the chromatic space and ensure whether the graph is 3-colorability. We hope the algorithm can solve more well-known NP-completeness problems more than the present theories.

Hadwiger's Conjecture is great to configure the chromatic space on graph coloring, which means any graph for any positive integer t can be contracted at most to a complete graph with t -vertices if it can be t -colored^{5,6}. It implies that the new algorithms on graph coloring might break the record of complexity on the issues.

Brute-force search is the simplest but worst complexity algorithm with $O(k^n)$ for a k -coloring⁵ in 1973. The dynamic programming⁹ with the bounded independent sets for k -coloring costs time at $O(2.4423^n)$ in 1976. The best result¹⁰ in reported algorithms on 3-coloring is $O(1.3289^n)$ in 2005, as a subexponential function. The best results¹¹ of the algorithm on 3-coloring are not more than $O(1.3158^n)$ in 2008.

However, although those improving algorithms

could run faster, they did not implement in polynomial time since the designs of algorithms are hard to avoid intertwining known and unknown coloring issues in the iterations.

In a chromatic space, we transfer the issues of graph coloring described in near-infinite dimensions to those in 3-dimensions. So, we ensure assigning one vertex in each iteration, so fundamentally manipulate the complexity of the searching algorithm.

In short, first, we destroy the edge recursion for pairwise vertices in combinatorial mathematics or set theory but implement the recursion for the edge in two divided subgraphs depending on the chromatic space; second, we move estimating 3-colorability of a graph out of the recursion.

On the other hand, the 3-coloring problem remains NP-complete¹². If we obtain that the algorithm for a 3-coloring problem is in polynomial time, then $P = NP$.

Here, every discussed graph is finite, undirected, simple, without loops and multiple edges; K_n is the complete graph with n vertices. Some graphic concepts are defined in the materials^{4,8,12}.

By the way, we follow the CPU in the the random access machine (RAM) model can perform any primitive operation in a constant number of steps, which do not depend on the size of the input. Thus, an accurate bound on the number of primitive operations an algorithm performs corresponds directly to the running time of that algorithm in the RAM model^{4,5}.

One of the milestones in the development of graph coloring is the concept: minor. The minor is a complete graph after edge contractions. The distinct but necessary colors are applied to color all adjacent vertices for a graph (total 23 papers)¹³⁻¹⁴.

The chromatic plane (CHP) is a plane in 3-D Euler space. The chromatic subgraph (CHPsG) on a CHP is one of the coloring subgraphs for a graph. We define that the colors used in coloring CHPsG on each CHP are different from those on the other CHPs.

There are three situations in the relation between a vertex and a CHP. We define the chromatic connecting number for a vertex to the CHP as how many different colors the coloring vertices on the CHP connected to this vertex are.

If the chromatic connecting number N_v is no less than the CHP(i) chromatic number t_i as

$$N_v \geq t_i \quad (1)$$

where i is the index of the CHP(i). We call the vertex a complete vertex to the CHP(i) denoted by CHP-CV.

If the number N_v is not more than t_i as

$$N_v < t_i \quad (2)$$

We call the vertex an incomplete vertex of the CHP(i) denoted by CHP-ICV.

In this situation,

$$N_v = 0 \quad (3)$$

We call a vertex not connected to any vertices on the CHP(i), an independent vertex denoted by CHP-IDV.

1. The design of the algorithm

Based on the concept of the chromatic space, we can assign a graph coloring into CHPs. In a CH-3D, we form two CHPs such as CHP(1) and CHP(2) and denote the chromatic subgraphs CHPsG1 and CHPsG2 as on CHP(1) and CHP(2), respectively.

In the initiation, we input the selected pair of the connected vertices in which one of the vertices is with the most degrees. So, the chromatic number of CHP(1) is limited to two.

If the tested chromatic connecting number N_v of a vertex meets formula (1), (2), or (3), we assign the vertex to CHP(1) or CHP(2) or manipulate the recursion to the different branches. So, we cut off the edge iterations for the connection search, and replace the smaller color sets for it, which means we replace color k for n vertices.

Corollary 1.¹⁵ *The graph of all minors on each CHP is connected completely if without disconnected graphs on each CHPsG.*

The proof of Corollary 1 refers to the material¹⁵.

According to Corollary 1, if we assign the vertices of a graph to CHP(1), the minor on CHP(1) is 2-coloring. If finding the connected subgraph in CHP(2), we know the graph is over 3-coloring; otherwise, obtain the 3-coloring vertex set. Thus, 3-coloring and 3-colorability both are solvable.

The flow chart of the designed algorithm is in supplementary information: part three^{S2}. We expand the recursion to while-loop to estimate the complexity. The pseudo-codes are attached in the method part.

The loop-invariants ensure the correctness of the while-loop in the designed algorithm, as follows,

- 1) One connected pair of vertices between the subG and CHPsG1 for any connected graph is findable at least.
- 2) At least one proper color of 3 colors to color the assigned vertex.
- 3) Only one vertex available to be assigned to CHPs for every loop in the while-loop. Then, it is removed from the subG.

In the calculation, how to find the loop-invariants is a kernel to destroy the exponential recursion. Then, we do not need to re-coloring the graph or searching for the possible cliques, patterns, or unavoidable sets, which the other scientists load us.

2. The complexity of the algorithm

According to RAM model⁴, we inherit the definition of primitive operations and count the number of primitive operations executed by the algorithm in the complexity analysis.

Primitive operations are for assigning a value, performing an arithmetic operation, comparing two numbers, indexing into an array, calling a method, and returning values from a method.

For a graph $G(V, E)$, the number of vertices is $n = |V|$. The complexity for function “sum-in-Row” is $O(n^2)$; also, for “*test-connect*” is $O(n^2)$. We embed the function “*enumerate-subG*” in the while-loop to decide the vertex in the unassigned vector to CHP(1) or CHP(2). We list the main analysis on the recursion of the while-loop in table 1.

Table 1 Complexity list in while-loop(i) of a k -coloring, $k=3$.

Label	Range(i)	O(x)	Explanation
L19	1 to n-2	$2*O(2)$	While-loop
L20	1	$(k-1)*O(2)$	How many colors
L21	1	$c_i*O(n+k)$	Embedded enumerate-subG
L22	1	$O(3)$	Branch 1: $N_v=0$
L23	1	$O(2)$	
L24	1	$O(n)$	
L25	1	$(k-1)*O(2)$	Branch 2: $N_v=1$
L26	1	$O(2)$	Branch 2
L27	1	$2*O(n)$	Branch 2
L28	1	$2*O(n)$	Branch 2
L29	1	$2*O(i+2+1)$	To CHPsG1
L30	1	$2*O(n)$	Branch 3: $N_v>1$
L31	1	$2*O(i+2+1)$	To CHPsG2
L32	1	$O(3)$	Branch 1

For the worst case, the for-loop is finding the connected vertex at the last loop. So, the complexity by counting primitive operations for the while-loop is

$$T \leq \sum_{i=1}^{n-2} [i * O(n+c) + (n-i-2) * (i+2)] < O(n^2)O(n) = O(n^3) \quad (4)$$

where i is the length of the vector for CHPsG1, c_1 and c_2 are constants.

Differing from well-known algorithms such as dynamic programming, or backtracking algorithm, and so on, we test the CCN SC of a vertex to decide to put it either to CHP(1) or CHP(2). Also, we separate 3-colorability to the test-connected from the recursion, according to the complexity in a chromatic space.

We list the main complexity for each step of the algorithm in Table 2.

Table 2 Complexity list for more taking-time in the procedure.

	Label	O(x)	Explanation
1.	L9	$O(n^2)$	Sum-in-Row
2.	L11-L13	$O(n^2)$	For loops
3.	L21	$O(n+k)$	Enumerate-subG
4.	L19-L32	$O(n^3)$	Embedded enumerate-subG in recursion
5.	L33	$O(n^2)$	Test-connected

So, the complexity of the algorithm for a 3-coloring graph is $O(n^3)$. A 3-coloring fore graph is a Polynomial problem. We either color the graph in three colors or obtain the result that the graph is over 3-coloring.

3. Proof on P = NP

It is well-known that a 3-colorable graph is NP-Completeness¹².

Lemma 1.¹² “3-Coloring is NP-complete.”

Proof of Lemma 1 refers to materials¹².

Lemma 2.¹² “Suppose X is an NP-complete problem. Then X is solvable in polynomial time if and only if $P = NP$.”

Proof of Lemma 2 refers to materials¹².

Thus, according to Lemma 1 and 2, $P = NP$ because the designed algorithm on 3-coloring is a Polynomial problem based on our algorithm.

Without loss of generality, if the given graph is not connected, we can separate the disconnected those in CHPsG2 on the CHP(2) by changing the Boolean

condition in while-loop, according to that the counting is more than the vertices of the given graph.

Learning from computational logic, we benefit from building the chromatic model of the imaginable space. We have not first been benefits from computer sciences since the four-color theorem. The algorithm to this century open problem is a little funning, such that from Chinese idiom: “the stewing soup makes the original raw food of digestion.”

Anyway, we designed the algorithm for 3-coloring that was proved in polynomial time based on chromatic space and cut off the iterations in searching, coloring, and assigning the undetermined vertices from the given encompassed scope of set theory.

We selected the vertex with the maximal degree and another connected to it, so the searching efficiency is improved. We utilized properties of chromatic space to decide the 3-colorability outside the iteration.

At last, according to our proof that 3-coloring is an NP-complete problem, and computational theory, we obtained $P = NP$. We hope the method might solve more problems with graph coloring.

Method for Pseudo-codes of the algorithm

Procedure test-3-colorable (G)

rem G is the Adjacency Matrix of the graph with n vertices

L1. var $SC[1:2]$, $colorM[1:n] \leftarrow NULL$: string

L2. var $V[1:n] \leftarrow (1,2,\dots,n)$, $row[1:n]$: integer

L3. var $subG[1:n] \leftarrow V[1,2,\dots,n]$: integer

L4. var $CHPsG1[], CHPsG2[], MG[]$: integer

L5. var VC : string

L6. var VA, VB, i, j, p, q : integer

L7. var bol : Boolean

L8. $MG \leftarrow G$

L9. $[VA] \leftarrow \max(\text{sum-in-Row}(MG))$

L10. $row \leftarrow MG[VA, :]$

L11. **for** $i \leftarrow 1$ **to** $\text{length}[row]$ **do**

L12. **if** $row[i] \neq 0$ **then**

L13. $VB \leftarrow i$

end.{if row}

end.{for i}

L14. $CHPsG1[1:2] \leftarrow (VA, VB)$

L15. $subG$ **remove** (VA, VB)

```

L16. colorM[VA] ← "RED"
L17. colorM[VB] ← "GREEN"
L18. i ← 1
L19. while subG[i] ≠ empty do
L20.   SC[1:2] ← ∅
L21.   (SC, VC, p) ← enumerate-
       subG(MG, subG, CHPsG1, colorM, SC, i)
L22.   if p > 0 then
L23.     i ← 1
L24.     subG ← subG remove V[p]
L25.     if length(SC) < 2 then
L26.       if VC = "RED" then
L27.         colorM[p] ← "GREEN"
L28.       else colorM[p] ← "RED"
L29.         CHPsG1 add V[p]
L30.       else colorM[p] ← "BLUE"
L31.         CHPsG2 add V[p]
L32.       end. {if length(SC)}
L32.     else i ← i+1
L33.     end. {if p}
L33.   end. while
L34.   bol ← test-connect(MG, CHPsG2)
L35.   if bol = TRUE then
L36.     print "The graph is Over 3-colorable"
L37.   else print colorM
L38.   end. {if bol}
end. {procedure}

function enumerate-subG(MG, subG, CHPsG1, colorM, i)
Le1.  var s[1:n] ← ZERO, p, q:integer
Le2.  var SC[1:2] ← ∅, VC ← "GREEN": string
Le3.  p ← subG(i)
Le4.  for j ← 1 to length [CHPsG1] do
Le5.    q ← CHPsG1 [j]
Le6.    if MG[p, q] > 0 then
Le7.      if colorM[q] ≠ "RED" then
Le8.        VC ← "GREEN"
Le9.      else VC ← "RED"

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end. {if colorM[q]}
Le10. if VC Not in SC then
Le11.   add VC in SC
Le12.   end. {if VC}
Le12.   else p ← 0
Le13.   end. {if MG}
end. {for j}
Le13. return SC, VC, p

function test-connected(MG, CHPsG2)
Lt1.  var bol ← FALSE: Boolean
Lt2.  var subM[1:n, 1:n] ← ZERO, s[1:n]:integer
Lt3.  for i ← 1 to length [CHPsG2] do
Lt4.    for j ← 1 to length [CHPsG2] do
Lt5.      subM[i, j] ← MG[i, j]
Lt6.    end. {for j}
Lt7.  end. {for i}
Lt6.  s ← sum-in-Row(subM)
Lt7.  for k ← 1 to length[s] do
Lt8.    if s[k] ≠ 0 then
Lt9.      bol ← TRUE
Lt10.   end. {if s[k]}
Lt10. end. {for k}
Le14. return bol

function sum-in-Row(MG)
Ls1.  var s[1:n] ← ZERO, p, q:integer
Ls2.  do [p, q] ← size[MG]
Ls3.  for i ← 1 to p do
Ls4.    for j ← 1 to q do
Ls5.      s[i] ← s[i] + MG[i, j]
Ls6.    end. {for j}
Ls7.  end. {for i}
Le15. return s

```

Supplementary information

S1. arXiv: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2104.13519>.
S2. Flow chart for the algorithm.

Figure 1 Flow chart to solve 3-coloring problems in polynomial time.

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